

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ROLE OF ENTODYNIMORPHA IN THE INTESTINAL MICROFLORA OF RUMINANTS

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Abstract

It has been established that rumen protozoa are strictly anaerobic and highly specialized ciliates that can only live in the rumen and similar habitats. These cilia play an important role in feed utilization and the environmental impact of ruminant livestock products. The rumen is a complex anaerobic digestive ecosystem, present in ruminants and plays an important role in the digestion and fermentation of ingested food, including starch, fiber content, etc.

Keywords: entodiniomorph, infusoria, rumen ecosystem, ruminants, species

INTRODUCTION

Any of a number of ciliated protozoa belonging to the order Entodiniomorpha are harmless parasites of the rumen and intestines of cattle, horses, and other herbivores. Entodiniomorphs are common and quite numerous: there may be 10 billion or more in a single cow. The cells are irregularly shaped, and the large syncytia are spirally arranged at the anterior mouth. Several projections are found on the posterior side of the cell; the largest is thought to serve as a rudder. It is possible that entodiniomorphs maintain a commensal or symbiotic relationship with their host, aiding digestion, and certain species digest cellulose. Entodiniomorphs reproduce asexually by binary fission and also exhibit the phenomenon of sexual union.

Rumen protozoa are strictly anaerobic and highly specialized ciliates that can only live in the rumen and similar habitats. These cilia play an important role in feed utilization and the environmental impact of ruminant livestock products. The rumen is a complex anaerobic digestive ecosystem present in ruminant animals and plays a crucial role in the digestion and fermentation of ingested food, including starch, fiber content, etc. This anaerobic digestion is entirely dependent on a number of microbial communities, including ruminal bacteria, archaea, fungi, and ciliated protozoa. Among these members, ruminal cilia account for up to 50% of the microbial biomass within the rumen. Their diverse biological roles, which include predation on ruminal microbes, oxygen production within the rumen, and symbiotic relationships with prokaryotes, particularly hydrogenotrophic methanogens, have profound effects on both ruminal functions and the overall performance of the host animal. Notably, ruminal cilia play a crucial role in feed digestion and consistently demonstrate significantly higher digestibility across a variety of measurements. However, within the spectrum of digestive processes, particularly those potentially associated with global warming and originating from ruminant production, ruminal cilia are recognized and account for 9% to 37% of ruminal methane production through direct or indirect combinations with ruminal methanogens. In addition, ruminal cilia contribute to the recycling of excess nitrogen within the rumen, paralleling the

limited nitrogen use efficiency observed in the host ruminant. The composition of ruminal cilia varies according to factors such as geographic distribution, diet, and between different animal species; thus, between 2 and 45 species have been identified. Interestingly, substrate preferences, host specificity, and antagonistic interactions between ciliate species give rise to four faunal types: type A (characterized by the presence of Polyplastron and Ophryoscolex), type B (characterized by Epidinium and Eudiplodinium), type K (including Elytroplastron bubali), and type O (comprising only Entodinium and isotrichids). These categories were proposed by Dehority and Imai, although previously mixed populations have also been documented.

Furthermore, the functional diversity of ruminal ciliate species makes interpretation difficult, especially in the context of ongoing microbiome studies, which often rely on morphology or marker genes. Moreover, the lack of a reliable reference database highlights the importance of unraveling the biological functions and metabolic contributions of individual ciliate species. Broadly speaking, ruminal ciliate populations are divided into starch-favoring species (e.g., Entodinium, which prefers simple sugars), cellulolytics (e.g., Epidinium, Ostracodinium, Eudiplodinium, and Ophryoscolex), and ruminant bacteria (e.g., Entodinium spp. and Diplodiniinae.) However, these classifications require validation through genomic or transcriptomic exploration, as much of the knowledge surrounding ruminal ciliates comes from indirect evidence such as defunations and in vitro monocultures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF THE STUDY

The effects of infusoria species have been studied extensively. Cultures in which a specific type of ruminal ciliate coexists with associated or free-living microbes using in vitro conditions are widely used.

The feasibility of studying individual ruminal ciliate species largely depends on their suitability for cultivation.

In addition to the use of appropriate washing procedures, electron microscopy (including scanning and transmission electron microscopy) supplemented

with fluorescent staining can visually confirm the physical associations between ruminal ciliates and their potential symbionts. Thus, if necessary, the use of antioxidant mixtures and stepwise freezing procedures can enhance the preservation of ruminal ciliate cultures during long-term freezing.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Ciliated protozoa are present in all wild and domesticated ruminants. Rumen ciliated protozoa are acquired by young ruminants by eating food directly from adult animals or contaminated with the saliva of such animals.

Digestion of cellulose by organisms in the digestive tract of herbivorous animals occurs in the rumen by microbial digestion. This phenomenon between animals and organisms occurs through symbiosis, that is, through a common life. Rumen microorganisms are natural microbial communities found in the stomach and consist of protozoa, bacteria and fungi. The rumen, which provides a good habitat for protozoa, which are divided into two groups: flagellates and ciliates, is high in terms of biological productivity. Flagellates are abundant in both the rumen and the intestine of hosts that do not have cilia. Their effect on rumen digestion is less than that of ciliates. Due to their small size, flagellates in the rumen are more difficult to recognize than ciliates. Although their numbers are generally too low to be observed, their density (10³-10⁴) cells/ml can only be seen when they are very high, in cases where ciliates are not found in the fauna. They are small in size and constitute a small part of the rumen biome.

Table 1.

Ciliates constitute the majority of protozoa in the rumen ecosystem. These cilia are between 20 and 200 µm long, are non-pathogenic, and respire without oxygen, i.e. anaerobic. Ciliates were first observed in the stomachs of domestic ruminants by Gruby and Delafond in 1843. Based on these observations, it was assumed that they would be important for the nutrition and metabolism of the host. Various factors such as the amount of food consumed, pH, turnover rate and frequency of feeding affect the cilia in the rumen. It seems to affect its composition and concentration. Ciliates can ferment and break down many types of substrates. starch, cellulose, etc. They ferment major plant components. This fermentation produces organic acids and is also essential for the nutrition of the animal as a source of carbon and energy needed by the host. Among these cilia, Entodiniomorpha ciliates produce cellulose and hemicelluloses (Table 1).

They have enzymes that act on them. In a study by Williams and Coleman, the degradation of starch and cellulose was observed in the rumen without cilia.

In addition, it is shown that the proteolytic activity of the rumen fluid is reduced. On the other hand, the body proteins of these organisms are an important source of protein for the host.

It has been reported that extracellular proteases secreted by ciliates carry out at least part of the proteolytic activity. This suggests that ciliates help in the digestion of protein-containing foods. Since ciliates digest bacteria quickly, they keep the bacterial population under control. Ciliates

play an important role in the nutrition of the host animal, as they are a more important source of nitrogen than bacteria. Ciliates reproduce by dividing into two parts. They can double their number within 24 hours. Ciliates living in the rumen can only survive and reproduce in these conditions. They cannot survive when removed from their host or rumen environment. However, they are not significantly affected by the removal of fauna and may continue to survive. Furthermore, since ciliates feed on bacteria, their presence in the rumen probably helps to maintain the health of the host

by preventing fermentation and associated loss of appetite.

When identifying species in rumen ciliates, the location and number of contractile vacuoles, as well as the size and shape of the skeletal plate, if present, should be considered. In addition, body shape and size, size, shape and location of the macronucleus, and the size and shape of the vestibule and cytoproct (cell anus) are morphological features that are also useful for monitoring rumen condition and the nutritional health of the animals.

Table 2. Classification of ciliated protozoa living in the rumen of ruminants

Phylum: Ciliophora	
Subphylum: Intramacronucleata	
Classis: Litostomatea	
Subclassis: Trichostomatia	
Ordo: Vestibuliferida	Ordo: Entodiniomorpha
Familia: Isotrichidae	Subordo: Entodiniomorpha
Dasytricha	Familia: Ophryoscolecidae
Isotricha	Diplodinium
	Enoploplastron
	Entodinium
	Epidinium
	Eudiplodinium
	Metadinium
	Ophryoscolex
	Polyplastron

The subclass Trichostomatia includes ciliates that are endosymbiotic in vertebrates.

It is divided into two orders: Vestibuliferida and Entodiniomorpha.

The ciliates of the order Vestibuliferida include several species of the family Isotrichidae.

(Table 1). In ciliates belonging to this family, the entire body is covered with cilia. Although the number of species in the family Isotrichidae is quite small, their frequency of occurrence is quite high. It is almost 100%. *Dasytricha ruminantium*, *Isotricha prostoma*, *Isotricha intestinalis* belong to the genus *Isotrichidae* and are found in all ruminants. In species of the suborder Entodiniomorpha, cilia are in the form of strips or cysts. The number and population density of these underwater ciliate species make up the majority of the fauna. With the exception of *Diplodinium* and *Entodinium*, they belong to the family Ophryoscolecidae. They have skeletal plates. In determining species in rumen cilia, the location and number of contractile vacuoles should be considered, in addition to the size and shape of the skeletal plate, if present. In addition, body shape and size, macronucleus size, shape and location, and the size and shape of the vestibule and cytoproct (cell anus) are observed in the same way. Rumen cilia, rumen condition, and microscopic examination of the animal are useful in monitoring nutritional health.

Ruminal cilia are known to produce hydrogen through carbohydrate fermentation. It is noteworthy that interspecific hydrogen transfer emerged as the main reason for the increased methane production associated with ruminal cilia. Moreover, this idea led Guyader et al. to discover a strong positive correlation between the number of ruminal ciliate cells and methane production. Direct evidence for this interaction

was obtained from co-culture experiments with *Polyplastron multivesiculatum* and *Methanosarcina barkeri*, which revealed significantly higher methane production accompanied by hydrogen uptake in the co-culture. Interestingly, this particular association accounted for one-third of the total methane production, whereas complete removal of ruminal cilia led to a decrease in methane production. Furthermore, it is worth noting that partial inhibition of ruminal cilia also had a mitigating effect on methane production, thus highlighting the importance of limiting ciliate-associated methanogen populations for effective methane reduction.

Although the contribution of ruminal cilia to nitrate reduction during methane reduction has been noted, the mechanisms involved remain incompletely understood. In addition, both in vitro and in vivo studies have observed increased metabolic reduction of nitrate and nitrite under faunistic conditions. This interaction highlights the role of ruminal cilia in ensuring the safe application of nitrate to reduce methane exposure. Commercial products such as Agolin and Mootral have demonstrated significant methane reduction in sheep and dairy cattle, but have limited efficacy in beef cattle. A meta-analysis of in vitro experiments showed that saponin supplementation significantly reduced total ciliate concentrations, with modest methane reduction effects. Furthermore, an analysis of sheep studies showed that methane was significantly reduced by dietary saponins, based on methane yield per dry matter intake.

Among in vivo studies reporting on ruminal cilia in saponin applications, two-thirds observed a reduction in total cilia number. A recent meta-analysis involving beef cattle and tannin supplementation supported the potential for methane reduction with a trend

toward reduced cilia number. In particular, different groups of ruminal ciliates, namely entodiniomorphs and isotrichids, exhibit different contributions to rumen methane production due to differences in their hydrogen production capabilities. Their different methanogenic associations have also been observed, as demonstrated in a study on the transfaunation of ciliate-free sheep inoculated with isotrichids. Given their role in interactions with methanogens, these interactions may differ depending on the ciliate species involved. Therefore, the mechanisms of methane inhibitors on total ruminal ciliate populations for synergistic or sequential methane reduction in complex rumen environments require further detailed investigation.

Although ruminal ciliate proteins have an amino acid composition that is superior to bacterial proteins for the host animal, their actual contribution to the host as microbial proteins is likely to be less than their numerical presence in the rumen; thus, their behavioral properties can ultimately be attributed to their overestimation of ruminal ciliate proteins, including rumen sequestration and bacterial contamination. Bacterial activity varies between ruminal ciliate families or genera. Therefore, considering both bacterial activity and ciliate cell number, *Entodinium* and *Diplodinium* spp. However, the specific effects of these ciliate groups may vary depending on factors such as age, diet, host species, and genetics. A study in monofaunated sheep showed that the presence of ruminal cilia resulted in a reduced transfer of microbial protein to the duodenum, an effect that was more pronounced in *Entodinium* - monofaunated sheep. Approaches such as the selection of target enzymes specific to ruminal cilia, screening of feed additives with anti-protozoal properties, and regulation of rumen transit time are also worthy of attention.

Numerous research efforts have been directed at elucidating the factors underlying variations in host feed efficiency, often quantified using residual feed intake in the context of the rumen microbiome. Thus, the low microbial and functional diversity observed in the rumen microbiome potentially allows for a more efficient use of dietary energy. The previously mentioned meta-analysis focused on the effect of defecation and established a link between ruminal cilia and higher dry matter intake, leading to lower average daily gain and consequently reduced feed conversion efficiency; a result that was particularly evident in low-quality diets.

The intriguing phenomenon of bacteria preferentially occupying specific bacterial groups, particularly key cellulolytic consortia, could potentially arise due to unbalanced dietary preferences among individual ciliate species. However, this hypothesis remains uncertain due to the limited number of predators tested to date.

Furthermore, attempts to improve the overall performance of animals through ruminal cilia-enriched vaccination, especially for entodiniomorphs, have not yet yielded significant improvements in either the pre- or post-weaning periods. Although the positive effect on diarrhea reduction has not been associated with changes in the rumen microbiome or ciliate populations, more comprehensive studies are needed to assess the advantages and disadvantages of stem ciliates, especially for young ruminants.

Furthermore, the composition of ruminal cilia could potentially influence the enrichment of bacterial groups associated with feed efficiency. Differential abundance of Proteobacteria in ciliate-associated fractions has been observed in various rumen studies, including marine ciliates. Given that these bacteria are hydrogen-utilizing, their association with ruminal cilia seems to be metabolically robust, allowing them to outperform other bacterial competitors in the faunal environment. Consequently, the reported relationship between ruminal cilia and rumen microbiota markers in the context of feed efficiency should be further investigated to facilitate their enrichment within the rumen.

CONCLUSIONS.

Infusoria belonging to the order Entodiniomorpha are an important component of the intestinal microflora of ruminants, playing a key role in the breakdown of cellulose, maintaining bacterial balance, and generally meeting the energy needs of the host. As a result of their activity, ruminants are able to digest fibrous plant foods with high efficiency. Therefore, the study of representatives of this order is of great scientific and applied importance in the field of animal husbandry.

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